

**IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF BITUMEN USED ON ROADS
LITERATURE REVIEW**

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Abstract: *At present, an important scientific and technical task is the creation of import-substituting, resource-saving technologies for the production of bituminous materials with improved performance characteristics. The solution to this problem can be the use of a complex additive in the composition of the SMA, which would not only prevent the delamination of the bituminous binder from the mixture and reinforce the asphalt concrete, but could also change the physical and chemical properties of the bitumen and improve the quality of the road surface.*

Keywords: *Crushed-stone-mastic asphalt concrete (ShMA), Petroleum road bitumen, thermoplastic rubbers, dispersed phase, asphalt , flotation tar , road surfaces, polyethylene bitumen mixtures, Surfactants - surfactants.*

Аннотация: *В настоящее время важной научно-технической задачей является создание импортозамещающих, ресурсосберегающих технологий получения битумных материалов, с улучшенными эксплуатационными характеристиками. Решением этой задачи может быть, использование комплексной добавки в составе ЩМА, который позволил бы не только предотвратить расслаивание битумного вяжущего из смеси и армировать асфальтобетон, но и смог бы изменить физико-химические свойства битума и улучшить качество дорожного покрытия.*

Ключевые слова: *Щебеночно-мастичный асфальтобетон (ЩМА), Нефтяной дорожных битум, термопластичные каучуки, дисперсная фаза, асфальтень, флотогудрон, дорожных покрытий, полиэтиленбитумных смесям, ПАВ – поверхностно-активные вещества.*

INTRODUCTION

Petroleum road bitumen is the main type of binder or adhesive successfully used in the road industry in the construction and repair of road surfaces, plastic, capable of withstanding low temperatures and temperature extremes, as well as applied deformations, without destruction. However, the specific operating conditions of such highly loaded road construction objects as bridges, overpasses, interchanges, etc. necessitate higher requirements for asphalt concrete pavements. Regulated grades of road bitumen are no longer able to fully satisfy these requirements. In addition, the load increases every year due to the increase in traffic intensity. The use of studded tires negatively affects the road surface. All over the world, work is constantly being carried out to create new modern road materials and technologies, adjust regulatory requirements for their physical and chemical properties in order to increase the

durability of road surfaces in modern conditions of their operation.

A.S. Kolbanovskaya And V.V. Mikhailov on basis analysis various representations O structure oil bitumen And research processes structure formation consider bitumen How spatial dispersed system, in which the dispersed phase - asphaltenes - swell in hydrocarbon dispersion environment, V various degree structured with resin. Based on this, bitumen is distinguished according to I, II, III structural type, which Can identify With colloidal systems "gel", "sol" And "sol-gel" (drawing 1) [1]

Drawing 1. Structure of bitumen I, II, III type

A great contribution to the study of modified bitumen belongs to such scientists as L.M. Gokhman , V.A. Zakharov, D.A. Rosenthal and others, as well as foreign P.D. Thompson, R.H. Lewis et al. [2].

Diyarov I.N., Kemalov A.F., Fakhrutdinov R.Z., Abdullin A.I. also achieved significant success in the field of bitumen modification. rubbers (polybutadiene, natural, chloroprene, butyl rubber), thermoplastic polymers (polyethylene, polypropylene, polyethylene vinyl acetate), sulfur, crumb rubber, organomanganese compounds, thermoplastic rubbers (polyurethane, olefin copolymers, styrene- butadiene n -styrene block copolymers) are used. The most widely used polymer-bitumen binders (PBBs) are based on styrene-butadiene-styrene block copolymers [3, 4].

The most popular polymer additives are thermoplastic polymers, which are able to repeatedly soften when heated and harden when cooled. Thermoplastics have a linear structure of molecules, and have the ability not only to swell in a dispersion medium, but also to dissolve in organic solvents. These include polyethylene, polypropylene, atactic polypropylene, polyvinyl chloride, polystyrene, polyiso butylene, elvaloy -AM (a copolymer of ethylene with butyl acrylate and glycidyl methacrylate), ethylene vinyl acetate , etc. [5 , 6].

Rubber-like polymers (elastomers), unlike thermoplastics , consist of huge chain molecules that can unfold when stretched, and when the load is removed, restore their original configuration. The main types of elastomers include styrene-butadiene rubbers (divinylstyrene), butyl rubber, ethylpropylene rubbers, etc. [7 , 8].

Thermoplastic elastomers (block copolymers of butadiene and styrene SBS) are amorphous granular polymers of a linear or branched structure, the molecules of which contain blocks of butadiene and styrene. Such polymers create a three-dimensional elastic network in bitumen, have a relatively low mass, and dissolve well in a dispersion medium 9, 10].

When using liquid road bitumen in asphalt concrete with both basic and acidic

mineral materials, additives such as iron salts (soaps) of higher carboxylic acids are used. Cationic additives effectively improve the adhesion of bitumen to crushed stone from acidic rocks, while forming chemisorption compounds such as silicatamines and carbonatamines (when fatty amines are used as surfactants) [18–19].

Walter's studies [11] showed that when the content of polypropylene in bitumen is up to 30% wt . the structure of the composition is finely dispersed , and the degree of dispersion depends only on the method of mixing. When the content of polypropylene 40% wt . phase separation was observed. The 50% mixture is a coarse bitumen emulsion. The dissolution of polyethylene in bitumen at high temperatures is confirmed by experimental studies on the combination of polyethylene with oils. A mixture of oil and polyethylene in a hot state is transparent, and at a temperature of 70-80 ° C begins to become cloudy and at a low concentration, the polyethylene crystals settle, and at a high concentration they form mixtures such as greases. The isolation of polyethylene from the polyethylene-oil mixture using isoctane showed that the weight of the precipitate was equal to the amount of polyethylene added to the oil. Thermogravimetric studies have shown that the degradation of polyethylene occurs at temperatures above 300°C. Up to these temperatures, polyethylene is a chemically resistant material. Since the combination of bitumen with polyethylene occurs at lower (180 ^ 250 ° C) temperatures, it is unlikely that it depolymerizes and forms radicals capable of interacting with bituminous radicals.

Polypropylene is very close to polyethylene in properties, therefore, when it is introduced into bitumen, the properties of the mixture are close to those of polyethylene bitumen mixtures.

Figure 2 . The dependence of the softening temperature of the polyethylene bitumen composition on the content of polyethylene of different molecular weights
 1 - low molecular weight polyethylene; 2 - high molecular weight polyethylene;
 3 - polyethylene wax

In accordance with the hypothesis put forward, further experiments were carried out to study the interaction of the elemental sulfur melt with tar in the temperature

range 140 ° -150 ° C for 20 minutes. and 80 min. After heat treatment of the mixtures, they were kept for 96 hours and the change in the viscosity of the mixture with time was determined. The main goal of this series of experiments was to determine the irreversible increase in the viscosity of the modified tar due to an increase in its average molecular weight during the interaction of double bonds of tar (the presence and concentration of double bonds had been established earlier) with sulfur with the formation of chemical bond bridges.

Figure 3. Dependences of changes in the values of dynamic viscosity at 60 ° C for sulfur-containing tar compositions in time (mixing time 60 minutes, mixing temperature 150 ° C)

To evenly distribute the additive in the mixture and to avoid clumping of the fibers, it must be fed into the mixer in granular form. The granules must be non-hygroscopic, i.e. not wetted by atmospheric moisture, and must be strong enough. The strength of the granules is of great importance when dosing into the mixer and for "dry" mixing of the mixture components. There is also the possibility of burning cellulose, upon first contact with hot stone material 180-200 ° C , namely, fiber bridges, with which it subsequently binds to bitumen. In order to increase the strength characteristics of the granules and reduce the hygroscopicity of cellulose, tars from an oil and fat plant were used - flotation tar and a fat composition. When using these tars, it is possible to obtain additional properties of the additive, which not only hydrophobize the fiber, but will also be surface - active substances that can affect the properties of the binder and, subsequently, the physical and mechanical properties of asphalt concrete [12].

To determine the optimal parameters for the impregnation of cellulose fiber with a binder additive, the effects of temperature and mixing time were studied (Figure 4). The choice of the initial temperature (20°C) was due to the fact that flotation tar forms a stable emulsion at a given temperature. A further experiment with lowering the temperature by one degree to 0 °C and raising the temperature to 60 °C showed that the emulsion remains stable and does not delaminate for a long time. The maximum temperature of 60 °C was taken on the basis that an increase in temperature above 60 °C reduces the stability of the emulsion, and also becomes technologically inexpedient

due to high energy costs. The intermediate temperature was taken equal to 40 °C. The mixing time of the emulsion with the cellulose fiber should be sufficient for uniform distribution and complete impregnation of the cellulose fiber. To do this, as an experiment, we took the spread in the interval of 15, 30 and 60 minutes at constant stirrer speed.

Figure 4 - Influence of temperature and duration of mixing of the stage of impregnation of rapeseed pulp on the adsorption of flotation tar .

From the diagram shown in Figure 4, it can be seen that with increasing temperature, adsorption on rapeseed cellulose fiber decreases. So for a mixing time of 15 minutes and a temperature of 20 °C, adsorption is 24%. When the temperature rises to 60 °C for the same 15 minutes, adsorption drops from 24% to 14%, this is due to the fact that with an increase in the process temperature, partial desorption from the fiber surface increases and the Duclos-Traube rule is fulfilled [13] .

Of the existing ideas about the structure of polymer-bitumen binder compositions, the most correct opinion seems to be that they are systems in which the polymer, at a certain content in the system, forms spatial structural frameworks responsible for the deformation characteristics of the composites. This position is in good agreement with modern views on the processes of structure formation in polymer solutions. There is a hypothesis that the polymer content at which it forms a spatial network in bitumen will be determined by the ability of polymer macromolecules to associate. In this case, the strength of the mesh is determined by the strength of the bonds in the mesh node and the number of nodes, and the elasticity is determined by the flexibility of the chains between the nodes of the mesh. In this regard, the ability of macromolecules to associate is of decisive importance for obtaining compositions with a spatial polymeric structural network. On this basis, all polymers can be divided into two groups. 1. Polymers whose macromolecules are characterized by a tendency to association. These include Polymers whose macromolecules contain functional groups and can form a strong spatial structural network due to the interaction of the latter with each other, or “conjugated” structures with functional groups of asphaltenes , forming chemical bonds, or block copolymers , whose macromolecules contain blocks that can

also form a network through interaction with each other, or conjugated with asphaltenes, but at the same time forming physical bonds. Polymers whose macromolecules show no tendency to associate. These include polymers whose macromolecules are capable of forming a spatial network only due to the physical forces of intermolecular interaction or random chain entanglement and interweaving. 5% polymer by weight. In this case, the viscosity of the resulting knitting significantly higher than the viscosity of bitumen, which can lead to technological difficulties in the preparation of asphalt mixtures at asphalt concrete plants [14]

to increase the cooking temperature above 160 °C [15], as they do abroad, since oxidized bitumen is used in Russia, which is subject to intensive aging at temperatures above 160 °C, while residual bitumen used abroad, withstand temperatures of 180-190°C.

The introduction of polyethylene into bitumen, as a rule, is accompanied by a sharp increase in the softening temperature and a decrease in the level of penetration of the material [16]. Studies of polyethylene bitumen compositions have shown that polyethylene is present in bitumen in the form of a dispersion, and the degree of dispersion depends on the method of introduction. The nature of the combination of bitumen with polyethylene has not yet been fully elucidated.

In the works of A.S. Kolbanovskaya, D.S. Shemonaeva [17], the destructur effect is exhibited by cationic substances of the class of high molecular weight amines and diamines, especially in relation to bitumen of the I structural type. These surfactants, being adsorbed on the polar (lyophobic) areas of the asphaltene surface, weaken the interaction between them and destroy the bitumen coagulation framework, which manifests itself in a change in the structural and rheological properties of bitumen in a wide temperature range. These additives have no noticeable effect on type II bitumen, while they have little effect on type III bitumen.

Separately introduced into bitumen, polyethylene forms a structural network only due to random links and intersections between long molecules [16]. To achieve high values for such indicators as elasticity and softening point, the binder must have a spatial three-dimensional structure.

According to studies [20], a three-dimensional spatial structure is formed by the interaction of polyethylene and polybutadiene rubber (Figure 1.5.1). In the case of using styrene-butadiene rubbers or natural rubbers, only swelling of the rubber particles occurs, without the formation of a structure (Figure 1.5.2).

Figure 5 . Image of the 3D structure of the butadiene rubber and polyethylene system

Figure 6 . Image of the structure of the styrene-butadiene rubber and polyethylene system

With an increase in temperature and dissolution time, the degree of revulcanization of crumb rubber increases. Accordingly, the particle size of rubber crumb decreases, the mixture becomes more homogeneous due to the “crosslinking” of the polymer and tar structures, which is confirmed by the increase in the viscosity of the mixture.

The conducted studies have shown the possibility of creating polymer tar compositions of road grades (PGV) at a cost that is in the same category as traditional road bitumen, but with significantly improved physical and chemical quality indicators. The possibility of using a serum as a vulcanizing component in the production of PGV, which promotes the crosslinking of polymer molecules, with giving the composition the necessary rigidity, is noted. The possibility of introducing rubber crumb into the composition of PGV is shown, which, in addition to increasing the volume of binder production and, accordingly, reducing its cost, plays the role of a "tightener" of CAB and polymer molecules, which increases the stability and strength properties of the composition.

A technology for the production of PGV based on the compounding of initial and deeply oxidized tars has been developed, which makes it possible to abandon the use of an expensive plasticizer and to halve the volume of sam that undergoes an environmentally "dirty" oxidation process. The possibility of producing a wide range of PGV with the predominance of certain physical and chemical indicators with the highest quality level by changing the ratio of modified polymer tar / deeply oxidized tar in the composition is shown. The test results confirmed the possibility of using PGV modified with polyethylene, gray and crumb rubber in the road construction industry, and also noted the advantage of this binder in comparison with oxidized road bitumen grade BND 60/90. A significant increase in viscosity is obviously due to the high concentration of the polymer in the tar, which is sufficient to create a single structural framework in the composition. Such an increase in the viscosity of the systems inevitably leads to an increase in their strength characteristics and, as a consequence, to an increase in the resistance to delamination [21].

Conclusion

In conclusion, an alternative measure to increase the strength of asphalt concrete is to improve the quality of bitumen with additional composite material or additives. In this case, several additives can be added to the bitumen. For example: polymer resin, polyethylene, thermoplastic, rubber, cellulose, flotation plastic, etc. At the same time, the physical and mechanical properties of bitumen are also improved. By adding several substances to bitumen: polyethylene (plastic), pieces of rubber and tire granules, it is possible to increase its strength and the resistance of the road to climate and vehicles.

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